

Trends pertaining to LIS review articles with a focus on categories, topics, and the academic age of authors

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Introduction

Review articles provide a summary and commentary on relevant literature. In addition to narrative review articles, systematic review articles are a major category of review articles, and they are valuable because they allow for the clarification of search strategies for relevant literature and the selection and analysis of related studies (Barczak, 2017). On the basis of the functions of review articles, three hypotheses are examined in the present study. The first hypothesis is that the growth rate of systematic review articles is higher than that of narrative review articles. The second hypothesis is that well-known senior scholars are the individuals who are most qualified to author review articles (Huisman & Koster, 1979). Notably, senior scholars are not always successfully invited by journal publishers, and review articles are not highly valued in academic publishing because they do not contribute new research results. The third hypothesis is that topics that have yet to mature or have not been studied for decades are not targeted by review articles (Bastide et al., 1989). To verify the three hypotheses, the present study explored the trends of review articles in the field of library and information science (LIS) for the 25-year period from 1996 to 2021.

Methodology

In total, 2,971 LIS review articles published between 1996 and 2021 were retrieved from the Web of Science (WoS) database by limiting the database search to articles that were classified as review articles, published in English and in journals classified under the “Information science and library science” category. Because some LIS journals (1,541 review articles) indexed by the WoS did not focus on LIS, we regarded these journals, which were listed in the Scopus and Ulrichweb databases, as non-LIS journals and excluded them from our analysis. In addition, the algorithms used by the WoS to identify review articles have led to unsatisfactory precision rates (Yeung, 2019). Therefore, we excluded another 645 nonreview articles after conducting a manual examination. Finally, a sample of 785 review articles was analyzed in the present study.

The two authors of the present study independently reviewed each article to determine its category (narrative or systematic) and topic. A temporary

topic classification framework for LIS topics was applied with reference to a study by Jarvelin and Vakkari (1990), and it was revised during the topic coding assignment phase. The two authors held multiple rounds of discussions regarding the inconsistent coding of categories and topics until consensus was reached. In addition, the authors of the included review articles were divided into three groups on the basis of their academic age at the time of the publication of their review article. For an author, the year of publication of their first article (i.e., first article indexed by Scopus) was defined as year zero for the calculation of academic age. For the publication of review articles, authors with an academic age of less than 9 years, between 9 and 18 years, and more than 18 years were classified as junior, mid-career, and senior researchers, respectively.

Results

Table 1 presents the distribution of LIS review articles by category and topic. The number of narrative review articles was approximately 3.2 times the number of systematic review articles, and the number of narrative review articles outnumbered that of systematic review articles for every topic. Among the identified 10 topics, “library and information (LI) service activities” accounted for the highest number of review articles, followed by “informetrics.” Notably, the “new technology” topic, which pertains to areas such as human-computer interaction, expert systems, and artificial intelligence was the fifth most reviewed topic.

Table 1. Distribution of research topics explored by LIS review articles.

Topic	NR	SR	N (%)
LI service activities	85	34	119(15.2)
informetrics	79	25	104(13.3)
collection development	77	13	90(11.5)
others	64	21	85(10.8)
new technology	66	18	84(10.7)
info. seeking	50	17	67(8.5)
classification & metadata	56	10	66(8.4)
scientific communication	38	21	59(7.5)
info. storage & retrieval	49	7	56(7.1)
knowledge management	32	23	55(7.0)

Total	596	189	785(100.0)
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Note: NR, narrative review; SR, systematic review; N, number.

Figure 1 reveals that the number of narrative and systematic reviews published increased over time. The number of narrative reviews published was substantially higher than the number of systematic reviews published. The gap between the numbers of narrative and systematic review articles published over time remained consistent over time.

Figure 1. Changes in the annual numbers of narrative and systematic review articles.

Figure 2 reveals an increasing trend in the number of review articles published for all topics. From 2017 onward, the review articles that explored the topics of “LI service activities” and “informetrics” exhibited the highest growth rates, and those that examined “collection development” grew at a slower rate.

Figure 2. Changes in the number of review articles by year and topic.

Among the 1,666 authors who authored the 785 review articles examined in the present study, most were junior researchers (889, 53%), followed by mid-career researchers (524, 32%) and senior researchers (253, 15%). Table 2 reveals that the number of coauthored review articles (414, 53%) was slightly higher than that of single-author review articles (371, 47%). Among the first authors of the 785 review articles, more than half were junior scholars (54.5%), and senior scholars accounted for the smallest proportion of first authors (14.8%). Among the first authors of the 414 coauthored review articles, 63.7% were junior scholars; in the 371 single-authored review articles, only 44.2% of the authors were junior scholars.

Table 2. Distribution of first authors by academic age.

Academic age level	Single-author	Coauthored	Total
Junior	164	264	428(54.5%)
Mid	130	111	241(30.7%)
Senior	77	39	116(14.8%)
Total	371(47%)	414(53%)	785(100%)

Figure 3 presents the trends pertaining to the four types of collaboration adopted for coauthored review articles with a junior researcher as the first author. Notably, from 2016 onward, junior authors tended to collaborate with mid-career and senior researchers.

Figure 3. Changes in collaboration trends for coauthored review articles with junior researchers as the first author over time.

Conclusion

The present study verified that at the time of writing, narrative review articles are still the predominant type of review article in LIS research. Except for the topics categorized under “others” and “new technology,” the other eight topics are long-established. Two library science-oriented topics (“LI service activities” and “collection development”) and two information science-oriented topics (“informetrics” and “new technology”) were the most frequently reviewed topics. In addition, the first authors of the included reviewed articles were mostly junior researchers, which is inconsistent with the second hypothesis. However, after 2015, a substantial growth occurred with respect to the number of coauthored review articles involving collaboration between junior scholars as first authors and senior and middle-aged scholars as coauthors. Further research is required to identify the factors contributing to this trend.

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